

GLOBALISATION IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract:

The article explores that a variety type of innovative technics which in teaching and learning situation can be enhanced for any language learners and people who want to improve their knowledge quality and develop their intellectual and linguistic abilities. Meanwhile, it is a great opportunity to use these methods for specialists in their own class. However, educational technologies require from teachers and students to be an innovator and researcher, plus to learn them diligently. There is an exchangeable line of ideas, experiences, problems which related to science, solutions of them, training of language teachers. Artificial intelligence (AI) is modifying a kind of aspects of education, as well as, dramatically being utilized to language education. Also, AI technologies and other special methods are productive for second and learners of foreign languages. It is a great opportunity to enhance their outlook and help their merits in the foreseeable future. The responsive technologies can be used in teaching various subjects within the pedagogical and philological sphere that will help developing a regardful willingness of future language teachers to carry out advanced approaches in the school practices or universities. The described current stage of innovative advances and their role are focused doing developmental tasks which support students' mental activities and implement these by themselves, saving learning time for further carrying out, high results from them, utilizing the best widespread practices in the class or at home, creating the conditions for remote teaching. It seems that an academic value is cognitive and intriguing.

Key words: Globalization, advanced approaches, remote teaching, portfolios, intriguing methods

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1.Introduction: The concept of modern education is improving day by day. And it has defined the purpose of activities of teachers and abilities of students. The enormous flow of database and technological development in today's world require personalized methods, special phenomenon of education, strengthening cultural-based foundation of society and various skills. Presently, the traditional education is saving more commonly for 21th century. As a result, the enhancement of innovative teaching and learning technics has emerged. These types of methodologies are focused by an advanced style of organizing educational and conscious activities. [1;3-8p.]

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2.Main part: It should be noted that the traditional teaching methods does not correspond to the international present-day changes in the world. For instance, the teaching things require creativity and professional innovation. Higher education teachers use the national or other types of technics to whole class. However, it is truly straightforward or tedious for contemporary educators at the moment, I think. It is time for exchanging the activities to intriguing and twenty-first-century ones. During classes or in university lessons, it is recommended that to implement the most prospective methodologies for enhancing the abilities of students and creativity, so as charts, clusters, using tablets, slides, collaborative search, cross-discussions or roundtable ones. Sure, exercises or with body movement games are perfect ways to teach, such as “Hot Potato”, “One, two, goal!” and others.

In a modern era, everything depends on information. One of the significant tool is Internet for doing our tasks, assignments, and educational purposes or etc. This never-ending data source and a communicational environment for intellectual new way. Furthermore, various resources are carried out by net from web pages with interesting materials.

Projects that to reflect students and how they themselves have grown up and changed in positive ways are surely in. Using portfolios of students is developing in education in general. If portfolios come to shows of acquiring, these are increasing popularity at a sharp race. It is great opportunity to catch efforts between a teacher and a student that it can be showed a progress and an enhancement. Via these portfolios, students can demonstrate their knowledge and authentic language using easily. Automatically, it is impacted upon self-monitoring and self-assessment of students more and more. [6;16-24p.]

It is contributed that using AI-supported methods and understanding many features of computer-based styles have been assisted to acquire language education and teaching. AI will be consistently amalgamated delving into learning education and updated technologies. In addition, AI is a digital technology that can be changed the environment of workplaces and institutions, also continued to become more profitable for teachers and contemporary learners. Equally important, automated writing evaluation (AWE) is provided students with feedback on their written-based work. Students are gained reliable database on the types of mistakes that they make. This can be seen in, the study of Turkish EFL students’ using of university that found for implementing works both automated and teacher-based feedback, demonstrated greatly level of automated one rather than manual labor advice.

The eventuality of the global health crisis in 2019 COVID-19 pandemic has caused more problems, as well as, a kind of positive effects to education and multifarious technologies. Hence, remote learning experiences or distance-based teaching systems were separated geographically in that situation. [7;129-136p.] Different learning materials, or exercises, assignments were sent via technological programs, such as Telegram or some kind of emails by students at a preferred time for the teachers. For example, In Philippines remote learning has been practiced well in high schools and secondary ones, however seldom practiced in elementary schools. The province of Laguna has adopted teaching this type one that try to study learning modality, namely, online, radio, or TV-based technologies. Using them is a common part of education system in Philippines, so they encountered most of benefits related to education, assessment of lessons, the enhancement of critical thinking with updated class games and etc. [2;17-21p.]

3. Conclusion: The world is changing dramatically. How we learn changing. How we assess and teach also changing. More intriguing and intellectual methods in the auditorium or in the class are rising rather than old, authoritarian models. Today's learning classroom is steeply diverse form that mid-to-late 20th century. The focus is not grammar, no longer memorization or other things. Instead of them, globalization and more collaborative and computer-based models are driven to empower our students or contemporary learners in real time.

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